

Urban Shrinkage and Light Pollution Dynamics in the Cities of Vojvodina, Serbia: Evidence from VIIRS Nighttime Lights

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Abstract: Characterized by rapid demographic decline, urban shrinkage represents one of the main concerns in Europe, with Serbia as one of the typical examples. The analysis of the nighttime light (NTL) satellite imagery serves as reliable data for assessing the dynamics of spatial distribution of the settlements and population. The focus of this research are eight settlements in Vojvodina, Serbia that have an administrative status of a City. Among them, only Novi Sad is experiencing population growth, while the others are shrinking. For the NTL data, the VIIRS satellite imagery data were obtained. They were analyzed as the mean annual values of the NTL for the periods April 2012-April 2013, and April 2022-April 2023. The years were chosen based on the data availability, and the population census years in Serbia (2011 and 2022). The aim of this research is to identify the correlation (r) between the number of inhabitants and the NTL intensity, as well as the changes that occurred between 2012 and 2022. Strong correlation is observed between the mean NTL values and population ($r_{2011} = 0.94$; $r_{2022} = 0.96$), as well as between summed NTL values and population ($r_{2011} = 0.86$; $r_{2022} = 0.98$). The correlation is moderate between the population change and mean/summed values changes of the NTL ($r_{m_diff} = 0.58$; $r_{s_diff} = 0.42$). Based on the results, it can be concluded that the NTL data are a valuable proxy for estimating population size, but are less precise for evaluating demographic dynamics and change patterns over time.

Keywords: urban areas; depopulation; nighttime light; satellite imagery; Serbia.

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